

Interactions of Cu(II) with Hydroxy Salicylic Acids

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The interactions between Cu^{2+} and 4-hydroxy, 5-hydroxy and 6-hydroxy salicylic acids have been investigated in aqueous medium and $\sim 0.1 M$ ionic strength by Calvin-Bjerrum potentiometric titration technique. It was observed that Cu^{2+} forms 1:1 and 1:2 complexes with these ligands in the pH ranges of 4-6 and 7-8 respectively. The complexation occurs by the reactions (i) $\text{Cu}^{2+} + \text{H}_2\text{L}^- \rightleftharpoons \text{CuHL} + \text{H}^+$ and (ii) $\text{CuHL} + \text{H}_2\text{L}^- \rightleftharpoons \text{Cu}(\text{HL})_2^{2-} + \text{H}^+$, (the ligand being H_2L). The stability constants of these complexes are determined and their relation with ligand basicities are discussed.

The possibility of a different type of 1:1 complex between Cu^{2+} and 6-hydroxy salicylic acid by the reaction $\text{Cu}^{2+} + \text{CuHL} \rightleftharpoons \text{Cu}_2\text{L}^+ + \text{H}^+$ is proposed. Evidence for such reaction is given by conductometric and potentiometric measurements.

TRANSITION metal complexes of salicylic acid and 5-sulfo salicylic acids are investigated extensively¹. However a systematic study of metal complexes of other substituted salicylic acids is still lacking. We have undertaken this work. 6-Hydroxy salicylic acid presents the case for two binding sites close to carboxyl group. The present investigation was undertaken to study the nature of complexes formed between Cu^{2+} and hydroxy salicylic acids in general and 6-hydroxy salicylic acid in particular.

Experimental

The details regarding chemicals, apparatus, chelating agents are described in an earlier paper². 2:6-dihydroxy benzoic acid was obtained from Schuchardt (Germany). $\text{Cu}(\text{II})$ was used in the form of its perchlorate and its concentration in aqueous solution was estimated by EDTA titration³. Conductivity measurements were taken by Systronics conductivity bridge.

Calvin-Bjerrum titration: The experimental procedure involved potentiometric titrations of carbonate free solution, of (i) free HClO_4 ($1.02 \times 10^{-2} M$), (ii) free HClO_4 ($1.02 \times 10^{-2} M$) + ligand ($2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$), (iii) free HClO_4 ($1.02 \times 10^{-2} M$) + ligand ($2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) + copper perchlorate ($4.0 \times 10^{-4} M$) against standard sodium hydroxide (0.15 N). The other details are given in an earlier paper⁴.

Results and Discussion

pK values: \bar{n}_A values were calculated by Living-Rossotti's expression⁵. The pK values were calculated by pointwise calculations. The values pK_1 , pK_2 and pK'_2 (Table 1) are ascribed to the dissociation of $-\text{COOH}$, $-\text{OH}$ group in ortho position to $-\text{COOH}$ group and $-\text{OH}$ group in other position.

The minimum value of \bar{n}_A for all the three hydroxy acids around pH 11.0 are remaining constant i.e., between 1.05 and 0.95. The higher values of pH could not be determined with accuracy because of the limitations of sensitivity of the glass electrode

Fig. 1.

Fig. 2.

and the sodium error. The pK value of one of the $-OH$ groups could not, therefore, be calculated very accurately. These values are obtained by the use of expression (6).

$$2p\bar{H}_{nA-1} = pK_1 + pK_2$$

pK values for dissociation of the two $-OH$ groups are 8.99 and 14.20 for 4-hydroxy 10.21 and 13.91 for 5-hydroxy salicylic acid respectively. The lower pK values corresponding to the $-OH$ groups in the 4th and 5th positions in the two acids; while the higher pK is for the $-OH$ group ortho to $-COO^-$. This can be inferred from the fact that $-OH$ group in the second position will have H bonding with $-COO^-$ leading to the stabilization of $-OH$ group which results in the higher pK value.

In the case of 2:6-dihydroxy benzoic acid the two $-OH$ groups are symmetrically situated with respect to the $-COOH$ group. The pK value of both the $-OH$ groups was 14.6. The neutralisation of the $-OH$ groups whether stepwise or simultaneous was also examined by conductometric titration. Two inflections, one at $m = 1$ and the other at $m = 3$ (where m stands for the equivalent of $-OH$ ion) are obtained (Fig. 1). The inflections at $m = 1$ and $m = 3$ are due to neutralisation of $-COOH$ group and simultaneous neutralisation of both the $-OH$ groups respectively.

Metal-ligand stability constants : The values of \bar{n} were calculated by Irving and Rossotti's expression⁵. The maximum value of \bar{n} was 2.0 around pH 8.0 indicating the formation of 1:1 and 1:2 complexes. The $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were obtained from pointwise calculations (Table 1).

TABLE 1. pK VALUES OF HYDROXY SALICYLIC ACIDS AND $\log K$ VALUES OF THEIR Cu^{2+} COMPLEXES

Name of the ligand	$(t = 30^\circ, \mu \rightarrow 0.1M)$				
	pK_1	pK_2	pK'_2	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$
4-Hydroxy salicylic acid	3.33	14.20	8.90	12.66	9.13
5-Hydroxy salicylic acid	2.98	13.90	10.10	11.41	8.98
6-Hydroxy salicylic acid	1.80	14.60	14.60	12.48	9.32

The complexation occurs by the displacement of H^+ ions from $-OH$ group ortho to $-COO^-$ ion. The $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values should therefore normally exhibit similar order as exhibited by pK_2 . From the Table 1, it can be seen that such an order is obeyed by $\log K_2$ but not by $\log K_1$. The relatively lesser stability of 1:1 complex of 6-hydroxy salicylic acid than that of 4-hydroxy salicylic acid is expected in view of strain produced in this chelate ring. This point is discussed later.

Cu^{2+} -6-hydroxysalicylic acid system : Fig. 2 represents the conductometric and potentiometric titrations of a solution having Cu^{2+} and 6-hydroxy sali-

cylic acid in a ratio of 1:1. The initial pH of the ligand before the addition of Cu^{2+} ion was 3.5. The ligand ion could therefore be represented as H_2L^-

or

Conductometric titration data reveals two inflections, one at $m = 1$ and the other at $m = 2$. The inflection at $m = 1$ is due to the neutralisation of one equivalent of H^+ ions liberated during the reaction $Cu^{2+} + H_2L^- + OH^- \rightleftharpoons CuHL + H_2O$. The pH was 6.5 at $m = 1$ and the value of \bar{n} at this pH was 0.9. The pH change during $m = 1$ to $m = 2$ from 6.5 to 6.9 was thought to be due to liberated H^+ ions by one of the following reactions (i) hydrolysis of Cu^{2+} , (ii) reaction between $CuHL$ and H_2L^- and (iii) reaction between Cu^{2+} and $CuHL$.

If hydrolysis of Cu^{2+} was occurring in this pH range precipitation would have obtained before $m = 2$. No such precipitate was obtained. To investigate this aspect, further, a similar type of conductometric titration wherein 2:5-dihydroxybenzoic acid was taken instead of 2:6-dihydroxybenzoic acid, was carried out. In this case the precipitation was observed at $m = 1.4$ and around pH 6.6. This means hydrolysis of Cu^{2+} is suppressed in the case of Cu^{2+} -6-hydroxysalicylic acid system. As regards the second possibility of reaction between $CuHL$ and H_2L^- there is no significant increase in \bar{n} values above one. The maximum value of \bar{n} before precipitation was 1.3 even in other titration when $M:L$ ratio was 1:2. The formation of a different type of 1:1 complex by the reaction $Cu^{++} + CuHL \rightleftharpoons Cu_2L^+ + H^+$ seems to be possible. The initial concentrations of the metal ion and ligand were $1.0 \times 10^{-3}M$ and the concentrations of $CuHL$, Cu^{++} and H_2L^- around pH 6.6 were calculated to be $0.65 \times 10^{-3}M$, $0.35 \times 10^{-3}M$ and $0.35 \times 10^{-3}M$ respectively. Cu^{++} reacts with $CuHL$ to form Cu_2L and since no free Cu^{2+} remain in solution hydrolysis will not be significant. However, precipitation was observed at $m = 2.2$ and at pH 7.0. Once the Cu_2L is formed, it will dissociate to give free Cu^{2+} ions which will hydrolyse. 1:1 complex Cu_2L is unstable because once $CuHL$ is formed the orientation of $-COO^-$ ion with respect to the benzene nucleus is fixed. For the formation of Cu_2L , the $C-O$ bond of second $-OH$ group will have to rotate in such a fashion so that it comes very close to the unbounded oxygen of the carboxylate ion. The chelate ring will be strained resulting in an unstable complex which therefore is formed only in a very narrow range of pH .

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